

Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles for catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol

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Abstract : The present study deals with simple and rapid method for synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Areca catechu* root extract as reducing and stabilizing agent. Stable silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were formed on treatment of an aqueous silver nitrate (AgNO_3) solution with the root extract. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized well by UV-Visible spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). XRD confirms face-centered cubic phase and the diffraction peaks can be attributed to (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (2 2 2) and (3 1 1) planes for these nanoparticles. The synthesized AgNPs were also found to function as efficient green catalyst in the reduction of anthropogenic pollutant 4-nitrophenol (4-NP) to 4-aminophenol (4-AP) by sodium borohydride, which was apparent from the progressive colour change of bright yellow to colourless solution, after the addition of silver nanoparticles.

Keywords : Nanoparticles, eco-friendly, 4-nitrophenol, green catalyst, *Areca catechu*.

Introduction

Nanomaterials provide solution to technological and environmental challenges in catalysis, water treatment and medicine^{1,2}. Many routes for the synthesis of metal nanoparticles use chemicals which pose high environmental risk as they are associated with chemical toxicity and biological hazards. Over the past two decades, many researchers have been focussing at total elimination or minimization of waste by adopting sustainable procedures using the 12 fundamental principles of green chemistry³⁻⁷. These green chemistry principles guide the researcher to minimize the usage of unsafe products and maximize the efficiency of the adopted chemical process. 4-Nitrophenol, one of the 114 perilous organic pollutants listed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), is a toxic and bio-refractory compound which can directly attack the central nervous system, liver, kidney and blood of humans and animals. The high stability and high solubility of this compound in water are the main reasons which make its conversion to safe levels a very difficult process⁸. 4-NP is one of the organic pollutants among many widely used materials in synthesis of many drugs, dyes, insecticides and herbicides, which makes 4-NP present at high levels in the industrial effluents, soil

and air. Further, it also damages mitochondria and suppresses energy metabolism in human beings and animals⁹. Hence, the reduction or conversion of 4-NP to 4-AP acquires great importance both environmentally and industrially. Detoxification of many organic pollutants is a tough challenge to many researchers and any significant contribution in this direction is of great value. Due to their good catalytic activity, metal nanoparticles have received great attention in reduction and degradation of many organic dyes. Among the noble metals, AgNPs have become the concentration of attention in intensive research, because of low cost and potential and emerging applications. Use of green synthesized nanoparticles through an eco-friendly option, is the most preferred option in a variety of applications. AgNPs have found wider applications as catalysts in reactions such as heterocyclizations, oxidation of ethylene to ethylene oxide and methanol reduction to formaldehyde which are industrially significant¹⁰. Moreover, AgNPs act as a redox catalyst in the degradation of dyes by electron relay effect between donor and acceptor molecules¹¹.

In the present study the synthesized AgNPs have been screened and found to be efficient green catalyst for the reduction of anthropogenic pollutant 4-NP to 4-AP.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) from Sigma-Aldrich, 4-nitrophenol and sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) from SD-Fine Chemicals used directly while *Areca catechu* roots have been collected from local agricultural fields. Milli-Q water was used in all the experiments.

Preparation of root extract :

Fresh *Areca catechu* roots were thoroughly washed with Milli-Q water and the roots (100 g) were ground thoroughly and filtered through Whatmann filter paper. Finally the filtrate has been centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 15 min to remove unwanted solid material.

Green synthesis of nanoparticles :

In a typical reaction procedure, varying quantity (1 mL, 2 mL, 3 mL, 4 mL and 5 mL) of root extract was added to 10 mL of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ of aqueous AgNO_3 solution. The reaction mixture was kept at 80°C for 15 min till colour changes to yellow indicating the formation of silver nanoparticles.

Characterization of nanoparticles :

The reduction of metal ions to metal nanoparticles using root extract as reducing agent was periodically monitored by measuring the absorbance using JASCO V-670 UV-Vis spectrophotometer till the solutions showed permanent yellow colour for silver nanoparticles. XRD spectrum was recorded for the centrifuged and dried sample of AgNPs using X-ray BRUKER D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ source ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). FTIR spectra were recorded using SHIMADZU, IRAffinity 1 spectrometer.

Evaluation of catalytic activity of AgNPs :

For the catalytic reduction of 4-NP, freshly prepared 2.0 mL of $5 \times 10^{-2} M$ NaBH_4 aqueous solution was mixed with 50 μL of $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ 4-NP aqueous solution in the quartz cell (1.0 cm path length and 3 mL volume). Then, 25 μL of the synthesized AgNPs was added into the above solution. A JASCO V-670 spectrophotometer was employed to monitor the progress of the conversion of 4-NP to 4-AP at ambient temperature by scanning a range of 200–550 nm.

Results and discussion

Green synthesis of nanoparticles :

UV-Vis spectroscopy is an important tool to determine the formation and stability of silver nanoparticles in aqueous solution. Fig. 1 shows UV-Vis spectra of silver nanoparticles at a fixed concentration of AgNO_3 ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) with different volumes of the root extract respectively. The gradual colour change from light yellow to brown for AgNPs was observed during reaction with varying quantity of root extract characteristic of the particle size of the nanoparticles as can be clearly seen in SPR. Initially, the maximal plasmon absorption peaks of nanoparticles showed broadening when minimal root extract was used (1 mL and 2 mL) followed by a blue shift with narrow band as the of coleus root extract was increased (3 mL, 4 mL and 5 mL).

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of silver nanoparticles formation using $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration of AgNO_3 with different volumes of coleus root extract.

The broad SPR band at lower quantities of the extract could be due to the formation of large anisotropic particles, since at lower quantities of the extract, synthesis of nanoparticles is not greatly favoured due to the absence of sufficient biomolecules responsible for capping and efficient stabilization. The same kind of results was also reported by Sujitha *et al.*, in case of gold nanoparticles using *Citrus limon* fruit extract¹².

X-Ray diffraction analysis :

The XRD spectra of the synthesized AgNPs is shown in Fig. 2, Bragg reflection peaks at 38.3° , 44.5° , 64.5° and 78.8° in the 2θ range between 30° and 80° which

can be indexed to the (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) planes of face centered cubic (*fcc*) crystals matching with diffraction pattern of JCPDS File No. 87-0720. Similar results were reported by Ashok *et al.*¹³ and Shashi *et al.*¹⁴ in the case of nanoparticles synthesized from different plant extracts. The size of the synthesized nanoparticles has been found to be between 35–70 nm using Debye-Scherrer formula.

Fig. 2. The XRD pattern of the synthesized AgNPs.

Catalytic activity of AgNPs :

One of the most important applications of the metal nanoparticles is to activate/catalyze some reactions that are otherwise difficult. As there is a great demand for many aromatic amino compounds in industry, the reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol becomes academically as well as technologically important. During the reaction, the absorption peak of 4-NP undergoes shift from 317 to 400 nm due to the formation of highly stable intermediate 4-nitrophenolate ion immediately upon the addition of NaBH_4 , representing to a significant change in solution color from light yellow to yellow-green. In the absence of AgNPs catalyst, peak at 400 nm remained unaltered for a long duration, indicating the inability of strong reducing agent NaBH_4 alone to reduce 4-nitrophenolate ion to 4-AP even though the reaction medium contains the electron donor (BH_4^-) and proton source (H_2O). According to Zhang *et al.*¹⁵, the catalyst brings

down the kinetic barrier created due to mutual repulsion between both negatively charged *p*-nitrophenolate ion and BH_4^- ion. Once the silver catalyst has entered the reaction medium, a consecutive decrease in absorption peak at 400 nm with concurrent appearance of peak at 290 nm corresponding to formation of 4-AP was seen. The kinetics of 4-NP reduction in presence of AgNPs synthesized with 5 mL of root extract was studied by UV-Vis spectroscopy. In Fig. 3 as the absorption band of 4-nitrophenolate ion at 400 nm decreases and disappears within 24 min after the addition of AgNPs, appearance of two new peaks at 290 nm and 230 nm, respectively (attributed to the generation of 4-AP) is noticed. The isosbestic point at 316 nm also provide further evidence to the formation of 4-AP as a result of reduction of 4-NP.

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra showing the reduction of 4-nitrophenol using NaBH_4 in presence of AgNPs synthesized from 1 mM AgNO_3 and 5 mL of *Areca catechu* root extract at regular intervals of 2 min.

In the reaction medium, the concentration of BH_4^- is very high and remains practically constant during the reaction. Hence, the reaction considered as pseudo-first order reaction for calculations. The kinetics of this catalytic reduction was also studied by plotting $\ln(A)$ against time where A is the absorbance at 400 nm¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Conclusion

The present work was focused on one step rapid synthesis of silver nanoparticles through an eco-friendly green method using *Areca catechu* root extract. The synthe-

sized nanoparticles were characterized well. SPR bands of silver nanoparticles from UV-Vis spectroscopy, suggested that with larger quantities of root extract (1 mL to 5 mL), the interaction got enhanced, leading to size reduction of spherical nanoparticles. It is inferred that the major constituent *Areca catechu* present in the root extract act as reducing agent to convert metal ions into metal nanoparticles. The stabilized AgNPs alleviated the transfer of electrons from BH^{4-} to 4-nitrophenolate ion by providing them a suitable reaction surface with lower activation energy resulting by the catalytic activity of synthesized AgNPs.

References

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